

Isonitroso- β -Ketoimine Complexes of Some Transition Metal(II) Ions

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A. Introduction

ISONITROSO- β -ketoimines I are expected to behave as versatile ambidentate chelate ligands, as they have four donor sites for coordination. However, only two of these are known to coordinate at a time to a metal ion. Metal complexes of isonitroso- β -ketoimine were reported by Taylor and Ewbank¹ as early as

I

R = H, alkyl, etc.

X = CH₃, OCH₃, C₆H₅, etc.

1926. They isolated an orange red diamagnetic nickel (II) complex by the reaction of isonitrosoacetylacetone with ammoniacal nickel(II) solution. This complex, bis (isonitrosoacetylacetoneimino) nickel(II), was

Taylor and Ewbank (1)

Nyholm and co-workers (2)

Ablow and Zubarev (3)

Das and co-workers (4)

assigned structure II. The same complex was prepared by Nyholm and co-workers² by nitrosation of bis (acetylacetonato)nickel(II) with potassium nitrite in presence of ammonium acetate at neutral pH. These authors assigned the structure III to the complex. Structures IV and V have also been proposed for the same complex^{3,4}. It can be seen that the structure assigned to the orange red nickel(II) complex are based on the assumption that both the ligands were identically coordinated to the metal ion. The fact that each of the ligands had a different mode of coordination was first recognized in 1970, independently by Bose⁵ and Lacey *et al*⁶. Based on ir, pmr and mass spectral data, these authors proposed the structure VI for the complex, in which one of the ligands is coordinated to the nickel(II) through isonitroso-nitrogen

VI

and imino-nitrogen, while the other through isonitroso-oxygen and imino-nitrogen, thus producing a hybrid ring structure. Since the recognition of the asymmetric structure VI, several nickel(II), copper(II) and palladium(II) complexes of bidentate and tetradentate isonitroso- β -ketoimine ligands have been prepared and characterized.

An attempt has been made here to review the transition metal complexes formed by different isonitroso- β -ketoimines and related ligands. Reactions of the complexes of these ligands, in particular, the amine-exchange reactions are also presented.

The abbreviations used in the text : M = metal, L = ligand, R-L = N-alkyl or N-aryl isonitroso- β -ketoimine, HIAI = isonitrosoacetylacetoneimine (4-imino-2,4-pentanedione-3-oxime), HIBI = isonitrosobenzoylacetoneimine (3-imino-1-phenyl-1-butanone-2-oxime), HIMAI = isonitrosomethylacetoacetateimine (3-imino-methylbutanoate-2-oxime), HIEAI = isonitrosoethylacetoacetateimine (3-imino-ethyl-butanoate-2-oxime), HIANI = isonitrosoacetoacetanilideimine (3-imino-2,3-dioxobutanilide-2-oxime), HIAPI = isonitroso-acetoacet-*p*-toluidideimine (3-imino-2,3-dioxobutrylo-*p*-toluidide-2-oxime), HIMI = isonitrosoethylmethylketoimine (3-imino-3-propanone-2-oxime) HIPI = isonitrosopropiophenoneimine (1-imino-1-propane-1-phenyl-2-oxime), HIBMI = isonitrosobenzylmethylketoimine (2-imino-2-propanone-1-phenyl-1-oxime) en = ethylenediamine, pn = propylenediamine.

B. Bonding of Isonitroso- β -ketoimines to Transition Metal Ions.

Isonitroso- β -ketoimines I may be considered as the Schiff bases of isonitroso- β -diketones or isonitroso derivatives of Schiff bases. Like β -ketoimines, these ligands can exist in three tautomeric forms: the isonitroso form VII, the keto amine form VIII and enol-imine form IX. Although, the tautomeric equilibria have not been investigated, it appears that the ligands predominantly exist in keto-amine form VIII. Further, each of these forms has four potential donor atoms of which only two get bonded to the same metal ion at a time, thus making the ligand ambidentate in nature. However, in all the complexes known so far the ligand is known to coordinate through the donor atoms of the imino- and the isonitroso-groups. Coordination of I involving imino-nitrogen and isonitroso-oxygen or nitrogen can give rise to three structures as shown below.

Similar structures can also be expected for tetradentate isonitroso- β -ketoimine and isonitroso-imine ligands. It can be seen that the three structural types X to XII differ only in bonding mode of the ambidentate isonitroso group. Such isomers may be called chelate linkage isomers, also known as bonding or structural isomers. All the three types of isomeric complexes are produced by I, depending on the conditions of preparation and other circumstances. It may be of interest to mention here that unlike the isonitroso- β -ketoimines the isonitroso(oxime) group of vic-dioximes and isonitroso- β -diketones coordinates invariably through nitrogen. The coordination chemistry of these ligands has been reviewed recently^{7,9}.

C. Preparation and Properties of the Complexes

1. Preparation

General methods for the preparation of the complexes listed in Tables 1 to 7 are presented here. Synthetic procedures which are applicable to the individual complexes are omitted and the relevant references are given in the Tables. A common feature of all the synthetic methods is that the ligand is produced *in situ* and then complexed to the metal ion. Sometimes polymeric compounds have been obtained in the attempted methods to synthesize the free ligand.

For example, isonitrosoacetylacetone reacts with en/pn in the absence of a metal ion giving rise to a sparingly soluble compound for which the polymeric structure XIII has been assigned⁹. Similar observations have

XIII

been made for the reaction of isonitrosoethylacetoacetate and other related isonitroso- β -diketones with en/pn ^{10,11}.

a. *Preparation from β -diketone and other constituents*: This procedure is applicable to prepare isonitroso- β -ketoimino ($R=H$) complexes only. A metal salt solution in aqueous ethanol is added to a well stirred solution containing an appropriate β -diketone, powdered sodium nitrite and ammonium acetate in aqueous ethanol or methanol (80%). Usually, the complex precipitates on keeping the reaction mixture for several hours or sometimes a few days.

b. *Preparation from isonitroso- β -diketone and other constituents*: In this method, a metal solution is added to an ammoniacal solution of isonitroso- β -diketone in an organic solvent. The complex is either precipitated immediately or sometimes obtained by concentrating the solution in vacuo. Alkyl/aryl amines or 1,2-diamines could be used in place of ammonia to obtain N-substituted and 1,2-diamine bridged complexes.

c. *Amine-exchange reactions*: This procedure originally employed by Pfeiffer and co-workers¹² is convenient and a general one. Most of the N-alkyl isonitroso- β -ketoimine complexes have been prepared by this method. According to this procedure, bis(isonitroso- β -ketoimine) metal (II) complexes and an appropriate amine in chloroform (other solvents like methanol, ethanol, iso-propanol, etc., are also used) is refluxed over a water bath. The time required for the completion of the reaction (generally 1-16 hours) depends upon the factors like the nature of the metal ion, basicity and concentration, bulkiness or the chain length of the hydrocarbon group of the reacting amine, temperature and solvent.

d. *Ligand exchange reactions*: According to this procedure, powdered bis(isonitroso- β -ketoimino) metal (II) complex is added to a solution of an unstable complex, bis(N-alkyl isonitroso- β -ketoimino)metal(II),

formed *in situ* from its constituents. If the equilibrium is favourable, ligand exchange occurs to produce a mixed ligand complex. The general pattern of the reaction may be represented as

Mixed ligand chelate linkage isomeric complexes listed in Table 3 are obtained by this method.

e. *Nitrosation reactions*: Generally, complexes of tetradentate isonitroso- β -ketoimine ligands are obtained by this procedure. It involves the reaction of a tetradentate Schiff base complex with gaseous nitric oxide or sodium nitrite. The reaction scheme can be represented as shown below.

It may be interesting to note that the nitrosation of XIV proceeds in two steps. The mono-nitrosated complex XV is first formed, which can be isolated. This is further nitrosated to produce di-nitrosated complex XVI.

2. Properties

Nickel(II) and palladium(II) complexes are brilliantly coloured orange yellow to red or yellow, while those of copper(II) are red, brown or bluish green. The diamagnetic nature of the nickel(II) and

TABLE 1—BIS-BIDENTATE ISONITROSO- β -KETOIMINO (R=H) COMPLEXES OF NICKEL(II), COPPER(II) AND PALLADIUM(II) OF THE TYPE MLL' AND ML'_2 $[XCOC(=NO)C(=NH)CH_2]_2M(II)$

M	X	Coordinated sites of the isonitroso groups	Ref.
Ni(II)	CH ₃	N, O	5, 6
Ni(II)	OCH ₃	N, O	15
Ni(II)	OC ₂ H ₅	N, O	14
Ni(II)	C ₆ H ₅	N, O	15
Ni(II)	NHC ₆ H ₅	N, O	15
Cu(II)	CH ₃	N, O	16
Cu(II)	NHC ₆ H ₅	N, N	19
Cu(II)	NHC ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	N, N	19
Pd(II)	CH ₃	N, O	13
Pd(II)	CH ₃	N, N	17
Pd(II)	NHC ₆ H ₅	N, N	19
Pd(II)	NHC ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	N, N	19

*Ligands denoted with and without prime indicates coordination of the isonitroso group through O- and N- respectively. This convention is used throughout the text.

TABLE 2—(N-ALKYL ISONITROSO- β -KETOIMINO)ISONITROSO- β -KETOIMINO M(II) COMPLEXES OF THE TYPE $M(R-L)(L')$

M	X	R	Refs.
Ni(II)	CH ₃	CH ₃ , C ₂ H ₅ , n-C ₃ H ₇ , n-C ₄ H ₉ , n-C ₆ H ₁₁	13
Ni(II)	OCH ₃	CH ₃ , C ₂ H ₅ , n-C ₃ H ₇ , n-C ₄ H ₉ , C ₂ H ₅ O	11
Ni(II)	OC ₂ H ₅	CH ₃ , C ₂ H ₅ , n-C ₃ H ₇ , n-C ₄ H ₉ , C ₂ H ₅ O	11
Ni(II)	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃ , C ₂ H ₅ , n-C ₃ H ₇ , n-C ₄ H ₉	11
Ni(II)	NHC ₆ H ₅	CH ₃ , C ₂ H ₅ , n-C ₃ H ₇ , n-C ₄ H ₉	11
Cu(II)	CH ₃	CH ₃	16
Pd(II)	CH ₃	i-C ₃ H ₇ , n-C ₄ H ₉ , C ₆ H ₅ , p-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	23, 24

TABLE 3—MIXED LIGAND CHELATE LINKAGE ISOMERIC NICKEL(II) COMPLEXES OF ISONITROSO- β -KETOIMINES OF THE TYPE $Ni(R-L_1)(L')$ AND $Ni(R-L)(L'_1)$

X	Y	R	Refs.
CH ₃	OC ₂ H ₅	CH ₃ , C ₂ H ₅ , n-C ₃ H ₇ , C ₂ H ₅ O	25, 26
OC ₂ H ₅	CH ₃	CH ₃ , C ₂ H ₅ , n-C ₃ H ₇ , C ₂ H ₅ O	25
CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃ , C ₂ H ₅ , n-C ₃ H ₇ , n-C ₄ H ₉ , i-C ₄ H ₉	25
C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	-do-	25
C ₆ H ₅	OC ₂ H ₅	-do-	25
OC ₂ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	-do-	25

TABLE 4—BIS-BIDENTATE N-ALKYL ISONITROSO- β -KETOIMINO (R=ALKYL) COMPLEXES OF COPPER(II) AND PALLADIUM(II) OF THE TYPE $M(R-L)_2$

M	X	R	Refs.
Cu(II)	CH ₃	CH ₃	16
Cu(II)	NHC ₆ H ₅	CH ₃ , C ₂ H ₅ , n-C ₃ H ₇ , n-C ₄ H ₉ , n-C ₆ H ₁₁ , C ₂ H ₅ CH ₂	19
Cu(II)	NHC ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	-do-	19
Pd(II)	CH ₃	CH ₃ , C ₂ H ₅ , n-C ₃ H ₇ , n-C ₄ H ₉	13
Pd(II)	NHC ₆ H ₅	CH ₃ , C ₂ H ₅ , n-C ₃ H ₇ , n-C ₄ H ₉ , i-C ₃ H ₇ , t-C ₄ H ₉ , C ₆ H ₅ , n-C ₄ H ₁₁	19
Pd(II)	NHC ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	-do-	19

TABLE 5—BIS-BIDENTATE ISONITROSO-IMINE (R=H OR ALKYL) COMPLEXES OF NICKEL(II) AND PALLADIUM(II) OF THE TYPE ML_2 and $M(R-L)_2$.

M	X	Y	R	Refs.
Ni(II)	CH ₃	CH ₃	H	40
Pd(II)	CH ₃	CH ₃	H, CH ₃ , C ₂ H ₅	39
Pd(II)	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	H, CH ₃ , C ₂ H ₅ , n-C ₃ H ₇ , n-C ₄ H ₉	19
Pd(II)	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	-do-	19

TABLE 6—NICKEL(II), COPPER(II) AND PALLADIUM(II) COMPLEXES DERIVED FROM PARTIAL NITROSOATION OF TETRADENTATE N, N'-DIAMINE-BIS (β -KETOIMINO) M(II) COMPLEXES.

M	X	R ₁	Refs.
Ni(II)	CH ₃ , C ₆ H ₅	H, CH ₃	10, 29, 30
Cu(II)	CH ₃ , C ₆ H ₅	H, CH ₃	30
Pd(II)	CH ₃	H, CH ₃	30

TABLE 7—NICKEL(II), COPPER(II) AND PALLADIUM(II) COMPLEXES OF TETRADENTATE ISONITROSO- β -KETOIMINE LIGANDS.

M	X	Y	R ₁	Refs.
Ni(II)	CH ₃ , OCH ₃ , OC ₂ H ₅ , C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃ , OCH ₃ , OC ₂ H ₅ , C ₆ H ₅	H, CH ₃	30
Ni(II)	CH ₃	OC ₂ H ₅	H, CH ₃	30
Ni(II)	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	H, CH ₃	30
Ni(II)	C ₆ H ₅	OC ₂ H ₅	H	30
Ni(II)	OC ₂ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	H	30
Cu(II)	CH ₃ , C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃ , C ₆ H ₅	H, CH ₃	30
Pd(II)	CH ₃	CH ₃	H, CH ₃	30

* In all the nickel(II) and palladium(II) complexes the isonitroso groups are coordinated through nitrogen and oxygen, while in the copper(II) complexes through oxygens.

palladium(II) complexes suggests the square-planar geometry around the metal ion. Copper(II) complexes are paramagnetic (μ_{eff} ca. 1.88 to 1.98 B.M.), a value expected for the monomeric copper(II) complexes without any magnetic coupling. These complexes may also have square-planar geometry.

D. Structural Investigation

Coordination compounds formed by monovalent bidentate and bivalent tetradentate isonitroso- β -ketoimines may be classified into two main structural types. Type I consists of asymmetric complexes in which the ligational environment around the metal ion is N,N,N,O (abbreviated as M-N₃O) giving a hybrid ring structure for the complex. Type II complexes are symmetric in which the ligational environment around the metal ion is either N,N,N,N,M-N₄ both the chelate rings being five membered) or N,O,N,O(M-N₂O₂), both the chelate rings being six membered). Only copper(II) is known to form complexes of the latter type with the tetradentate ligands.

Infra-red (ir), proton magnetic resonance (pmr), electron spin resonance (esr) and nitrogen ls photoelectron spectroscopic techniques have been used to characterize the two structural types of the complexes.

1. Isonitroso- β -ketoimine (R=H) complexes, MLL' ; ML_2

Isonitroso- β -ketoimines (R=H) are known to form symmetric as well as asymmetric complexes depending upon the metal ion and the terminal substituent X of the ligand. Except in the case of M(IANI)₂ and M(IAPI)₂ (M=Cu, Pd), asymmetric structure XVII has been assigned^{5,6,13-16} to the complexes listed in Table 1.

TABLE 8—IR ABSORPTION BANDS (IN cm^{-1}) OF MLL' AND ML_2 COMPLEXES

Complex	$\nu_{C=O}$		ν_{N-H}		ν_{N-O} in mull	
	in mull	in CHCl ₃	in mull	in CHCl ₃	N-bonded	O-bonded
Ni(IAI)(IAI')	1650	1672	3230 sh	3225	1210	1098'
	1680	1697	3258	3265		
Ni(IEAI)(IEAI')	1700	1700 sh	3179	3220	1198	1100
	1720	1715	3310	3375		
Ni(IMAI)(IMAI)	1704	1706	3179	3204	1202	1102
	1729	1725	3312	3354		
Ni(IBI)(IBI')	1638	1667 b	3160	3120	1188	1102
	1667		3311	3367		
Ni(IANI)(IANI')	1675 b		3208	3225	1208	1155
	1683 sh	1669	3305	3365		
Cu(IAI)(IAI')	1650	1666	3204	3292	1225	1150
	1666 sh	1666 b	3240	3250		
Pd(IAI)(IAI')	1655	—	3200 sh	—	1200	1150
	1684		3250			
Pd(IAI) ₂	1655	—	3260	—	1225	
Cu(IANI) ₂	1650	—	3220	—	1210	
Cu(IAPI) ₂	1670	—	3355	—	1200	
Pd(IANI) ₂	1665	—	3355	—	1220	
Pd(IAPI) ₂	1670	—	3260	—	1210	

b = broad ; sh = shoulder

First and second row frequencies correspond to those of L and L' ligands, respectively.

FIG 1 IR SPECTRA OF (a) Ni(II) and (b) Pd(II) in NUJOL MULL

FIG 2 PMR SPECTRUM OF Ni(II) IN CCl₄

2. (*N*-alkyl isonitroso- β -ketoimino) (isonitroso- β -ketoimino) *M*(II) complexes, *M*(*R-L*)(*L'*)

Nickel(II) complexes of this type were first prepared by Bose *et al*¹³ by the reaction of XVII (X=CH₃) with primary amines, as represented by eqn. 2. The complexes of this type are

listed in Table 2. All the nickel(II) complexes are suggested to have asymmetric structure XXI on the basis of their ir and pmr spectral data^{11,13,14}. The asymmetric structure has also been confirmed by nitrogen 1s X-ray photoelectron spectra²⁰. A representative deconvoluted spectrum is shown in Fig. 3, while the observed nitrogen 1s ionization potentials are given in Table 9. Four nitrogen 1s photoelectron signals are expected for the structure of the type XXI. However, the spectra of Ni(R-IAI)

(IAI') show three nitrogen 1s signals around 399, 400 & 401 eV with relative intensities ca. 2 : 1 : 1 respectively. These signals have been assigned to nitrogens of M-NR + M-NH, M-NO and M-ON respectively. Probably the difference in the ionization potentials for nitrogen 1s electrons of NR and NH moieties are very small. This gives, therefore, a single signal around 399 eV.

FIG 3 NITROGEN 1S PHOTOELECTRON SPECTRUM OF Ni(II)-IAI(IAI')

The final proof, for the proposed structure has come from X-ray single crystal structure for the molecule Ni(CH₃-IAI) (IAI')^{21,22}. The molecule is essentially planar with significant interaction between N-H proton of the six membered chelate ring and the projecting oxygen of the N-O group, which is cis to it. The N-O bond length (1.26 Å) of the five membered chelate ring is much shorter than the average N-O bond length (1.36 Å) observed so far. The Ni-N distance (1.81 Å) of the six membered chelate ring is significantly shorter (average, 1.89 Å) than that of the five membered chelate ring.

The palladium(II) analogues of XXI, R = α -branched alkyl, C₆H₅, C₆H₄CH₃ etc. and X=CH₃ are also known to have same asymmetric structure^{23,24}.

Only one copper(II) complex, Cu(Me-IAI) (IAI'), of the structural type XXI is reported¹⁶. This complex has been prepared by the chelate exchange method involving Cu(IAI)(IAI') and Cu(CH₃-IAI)₂ in dry benzene.

3. Mixed ligand chelate linkage isomeric complexes, M(R-L₁)(L') and M(R-L)(L')

Of the metal ions investigated only nickel(II) is known to form complexes of this type and are listed in Table 3. These complexes are obtained by the ligand exchange reaction (section C, method 4) between the stable parent nickel(II) complex of the type NiLL' and an unstable dialkyl complex of the type Ni(R-L)₂. The formation of mixed ligand complexes Ni(R-L₁)(L') may be explained as follows:

Step i: The dialkyl complex is first produced *in situ* by adding nickel(II) acetate tetrahydrate to a solution of appropriate isonitroso-β-diketone and a primary alkylamine. The unstable dialkyl complex is believed to have trans symmetric structure XXIII.

Step ii: In the presence of XXIII, the added parent nickel(II) complex of the structural type XVII (NiLL') rearranges to a symmetric structure XXIV with isonitroso-oxygen coordination.

The mixed ligand complexes show the combined spectral features of NiLL'₁ and Ni(R-L)(L'). Further, the ir and pmr bands of Ni(R-L₁)(L') is a superposition of the ir and pmr bands of R-L₁ and L'. Similar is the case with Ni(R-L)(L') also. Based on these results, the complexes²⁶ are suggested to have asymmetric structure XXV. It is significant to note that in the structure XXV and its chelate linkage isomer, the N-alkyl ligand (R=alkyl group) is always coordinated

to the metal (II) through isonitroso-nitrogen, while the imino ligand (L' or L'₁) through isonitroso-oxygen.

Step iii: In this step, XXIII and XXIV undergo ligand exchange reaction giving a stable mixed ligand complex XXV, Ni(R-L₁)(L'). Analogously, the formation of the linkage isomer of XXV, Ni(R-L)(L'₁), can be explained.

Mixed ligand complexes of the type Ni(R-IMI)(IAI'), where R= straight chain alkyl group, have been reported²⁶. However, the linkage isomeric complexes, Ni(R-IAI)(IMI'), have not been isolated. It is suggested that in Ni(R-IMI)(IAI') the ligands R-IMI

Interestingly, each of the isomers A and B of nickel(II) isomerizes in chloroform to give an equilibrium mixture of two isomers (N and O bonded) in the temperature range 25-40°C. This reaction is irreversible. However, such isomerization reaction is not favoured by the palladium(II) analogues.

In contrast to the nickel(II) and palladium(II) complexes, copper(II)³⁰ forms a single isomer with XXVIII ($R_1 = H, CH_3$; $X = CH_3, C_6H_5$). The ir spectra of these complexes show the C=O absorption in the region 1650-1690 cm^{-1} . The position of this band compares well with the O-bonded isomer of the corresponding nickel(II) complexes. Hence, structure of the type XXXI has been assigned for these complexes. The O-bonded N-O occurs as an intense band around 1150 cm^{-1} . The esr spectral data of the complexes are also consistent with the proposed structure. The first derivative esr spectra (a representative one is shown in Fig. 5) show equally spaced four signals due to the interaction of the unpaired electron with Cu^{2+} ($I = 3/2$). Of these, the first two high field signals are further split into five components with intensity ratio of 1 : 2 : 3 : 2 : 1. The average values for esr parameters

are 2.07 (g), 90.0 gauss (A_{Cu}), 13.0 gauss (A_N) and 0.79 (covalency factor, α^2). These values are in the range expected for the square-planar copper(II) complexes having N_2O_2 ligational environment around the metal ion³¹⁻³⁴.

The isonitroso-oxygen coordination has been shown by X-ray single crystal structure of XXXI ($M = Cu, R_1 = H$ and $X = CH_3$)³⁵. The molecular structure of this complex shows that the acetylacetonimine chelate ring is essentially planar with significant delocalization of the π -electrons, while the other two chelate rings show deviation from the planarity. The crystal structure indicates that the angle formed between Cu-Cu direction and coordination plane is 81.8°, so that the whole structure can be considered as formed by discrete molecules, which seem to be joined together in dimers through a very feeble metal-metal interaction.

The tetradentate ligands of the second type XXIX are known to coordinate through imino-nitrogens and the square-planar geometry is completed by coordination of donor atoms of the isonitroso groups. The two C=O groups remain non-coordinated. Since the isonitroso group can coordinate bifunctionally three structures XXXII to XXXIV are expected for the complexes formed by XXIX. The structure of the type XXXII

was favoured for the nickel(II) and palladium(II) complexes of XXIX ($R_1 = H$ and $X = CH_3$) by the previous investigators^{3,9,28,36}. However, the ir spectra^{10,11} of these complexes in nujol mull and in chloroform show two distinct bands in the region 1650-1700 cm^{-1} . The frequencies around 1150 cm^{-1} and 1200 cm^{-1} are assignable to O- and N-bonded N-O moiety respectively. These results are consistent with the structure XXXIV. Similar structure has been assigned to all the nickel(II) and palladium(II) complexes with different substituents X and R_1 ^{10,11,37}. The structure has been also supported by pmr data. Further, preliminary single crystal structure of one of the nickel(II) complexes ($R_1 = H$ and $X = CH_3$) clearly suggests N_2O ligational environment around the metal ion³⁸. The hybrid ring structure is retained when one of X's is substituted by different groups like OC_2H_5 or C_6H_5 ¹⁰. It may be noted in the proposed structure XXXIV that the isonitroso groups of the same ligand are coordinated differently to the same metal ion. The isomerism of this type may be termed 'intra-ligand chelate linkage isomerism'. This is to be distinguished from the aforementioned two kinds of linkage isomerisms.

FIG 5 FIRST DERIVATIVE ESR SPECTRUM OF XXXI.
M = Cu(II), $R_1 = H$ and $X = CH_3$, in $CHCl_3$ at 20°C

Unlike the complexes of nickel(II) and palladium(II), copper(II) complexes of XXIX with $R_1 = H, CH_3$ and $X = CH_3, C_6H_5$, show a single $C=O$ frequency in the region 1650-1690 cm^{-1} . The position of this band compares well with that of the O-bonded chelate ring of the corresponding nickel(II) complex. Symmetric bonding of the isonitroso groups as in XXXIII has, therefore, been assigned^{8,7} to the copper(II) complexes. The O-bonded N-O stretch appears around 1150 cm^{-1} . ESR data also support similar structure. Incidentally, three different coloured compounds¹⁰, dark brown, black and reddish brown, having the same stoichiometry have been obtained for XXXIII ($R=H, X=CH_3$) depending upon the experimental conditions employed for the preparation as given by eqns. 3 to 5.

The solid state ir spectra of the three forms are virtually identical except for a small shift ($\pm 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) in the $C=O$ and N-O frequencies. The three coloured forms appear to be crystalline modifications having the same molecular structure XXXIII.

E. Complexes of the Related Ligands

The ligands isonitroso-imines XXXV are very similar to the isonitroso- β -ketoimines I, since they possess the common groups, $-C-C-$. These ligands

XXXV

XXXV may, therefore, be considered as derived from I by replacing $X-C-$ moiety by an alkyl or aryl group.

It can be seen from Table 7 that majority of the complexes of this series of ligands are formed by palladium(II),

TABLE 10 - HAMMETT VALUES FOR X^a AND NON-BONDED $C=O$ STRETCHING FREQUENCIES^b.

Substituent X	Hammett value σ_X	$\nu_{C=O}$ in cm^{-1}	
		isonitroso N-bonded	isonitroso O-bonded
$-CH_3$	-0.170	1662	1695
$-OCH_3$	-0.268	1700	1724
$-OC_2H_5$	-0.240	1698	1716
$-C_6H_5$	-0.010	1650	1666

^a Taken from reference (42).

^b The values represent the average frequencies of isonitroso-oxygen and isonitroso-nitrogen bonded isonitroso- β -ketoimino nickel(II) complexes

whereas only one nickel(II) complex with $R=H$ and $X=Y=CH_3$ is known. On the basis of ir, pmr and nitrogen is photoelectron spectral data all the complexes are suggested to have trans symmetric structure XXXVI, in which both the ligands are identically coordinated through isonitroso-nitrogen and imino-nitrogen^{1,9,9,40}.

F. Infrared Correlation

It has been pointed out in the foregoing sections that the non-coordinated $C=O$ frequency is highly sensitive to the bonding site of the isonitroso group of the ligand moiety. It also depends on the nature of the terminal substituent X. The data show that the $C=O$ frequency of the N-bonded moiety always appears at lower wave numbers (by ca. 25 cm^{-1}) than that of the O bonded chelate moiety. The average $C=O$ frequencies of the N and O-bonded chelate rings are listed in Table 10. A plot of $C=O$ frequency vs. σ_X (Fig. 6) illustrates the linear relationship between the two.

FIG 6 PLOT OF HAMMETT CONSTANT (σ_X) VS $\nu_{C=O}$ OF ISONITROSO-N- AND O-COORDINATED MOETIES OF BIS (ISONITROSO- β -KETOIMINO) NICKEL (II) COMPLEXES

G. Factors influencing the ambidentate coordination of the isonitroso group

Structural elucidation of the complexes given above (Sections D and E) clearly demonstrates that the isonitroso group of isonitroso- β -ketoimines and the related ligands can coordinate through nitrogen and/or oxygen to a metal ion. This mode of coordination is found to be influenced by a number of factors. Various explanations have been put forward to account for the

factors that modify the coordination of an ambidentate group. Some of these factors have already been discussed in a review by Norbury²¹ in connection with the coordination compounds of chalcogenocyanates.

The available data suggest that the site of coordination of an isonitroso group depends on factors like metal ion, steric effects due to the size of the metal ion and bulkiness of substituent R on the azomethine nitrogen, electronic effects due to the terminal substituent X as well as the azomethine nitrogen substituent R, solvent and temperature of the medium. Before discussing each of these effects separately, it is appropriate to mention that it is almost impossible to offer an explanation for the preferred bonding mode of the isonitroso group by a single factor.

1. *Steric effects*: Of the metal ions investigated nickel(II) prefers asymmetric ligational environment (Ni-N₃O) in all its complexes. The peculiar configuration adopted by nickel(II) is independent of the electronic properties of the substituents R and X. The hybrid ring structure is also retained in the common organic solvents^{5,11}. However, no nickel(II) complex of the structural type Ni(R-L)₂ is known so far, although such a species is postulated to be present *in situ* during the process of preparation. The failure to obtain nickel(II) complexes having symmetric structure has been accounted¹³ by steric interference between the projecting N-O and N-R, when R = H, alkyl or aryl, in *cis* positions. This is expected due to the smaller size of nickel(II).

It is, however, impossible to separate steric factors from the electronic factors completely. Steric effect is expected to be less significant in case of copper(II) and palladium(II) because of their larger ionic size than that of nickel(II). The isolation of ML₂ as well as M(R-L)₂ (M = Cu, Pd; R = straight chain alkyl group) does support this view. However, if the bulkiness of R is increased sufficiently, steric effect should be operative even in case of copper(II). This is apparent by the absence of Cu(R-L)₂ complexes^{16,19} with R = i-C₃H₇, i-C₄H₉ etc. As expected palladium(II) forms dialkyl symmetric complexes even with these substituents¹⁹. The exclusive behaviour of the nickel(II) to form asymmetric complexes seems to be dominated mainly by the steric effect. The only apparent exception to this generalization is Ni(IMI)₂. However, the symmetric structure (Ni-N₄) proposed for this complex needs further investigation.

2. *Electronic effects*: The preferred bonding mode of an ambidentate group may be influenced by the electronic effects of the substituents in the neighbourhood. Table 11 summarizes the coordinating behaviour of the isonitroso group with respect to the substituents R and X and the metal ion. It can be seen that unlike in the case of nickel(II), the isonitroso group displays varied bonding modes with copper(II) and palladium(II) depending upon the nature of R and X. Thus, the complexes M(IAI)(IAI') (M = Cu, Pd) have asymmetric

TABLE 11—OBSERVED MODES OF BONDING OF THE ISONITROSO GROUP*

Metal	R	X	donor sites of the isonitroso group
Ni(II)	CH ₃ , OCH ₃ , OC ₂ H ₅ , C ₆ H ₅ , NHC ₆ H ₅	H, alkyl or aryl	N, O
Cu(II), Pd(II)	CH ₃	H	N, O
Pd(II)	CH ₃	H	N, N
Cu(II), Pd(II)	CH ₃	Non bulky alkyl	N, N
Cu(II), Pd(II)	NHC ₆ H ₅ , NHC ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	H, alkyl or aryl	N, N

* In the 1,2-diamine bridged isonitroso-β-ketoimine copper(II) complexes the donor sites of the isonitroso groups are O, O, while N, O in the nickel(II) and palladium(II) complexes.

structure, while M(R-IAI)₂ are symmetric when R is a straight chain alkyl group. The difference in the coordination behaviour of the two series of compounds may be attributed to the electronic effects of the substituent R. In the former complexes when the substituent is a proton, which is an electronegative atom, N and/or O-coordination is favoured. On the other hand in the M(R-L)₂ complexes with electron donor alkyl group as the substituent, can polarize the isonitroso-nitrogen more than oxygen. This promotes the N-coordination. The same argument holds for N-coordination of the N-alkyl isonitroso-β-ketoimine ligands in Ni(R-L)(L'), Ni(R-L₁)(L'), Ni(R-L)(L₁') and M(R-L)₂ (M = Cu, Pd; L = IANI, IAPI) series of compounds. The symmetrical coordination of both the ligands in Pd(R-L)₂ L = IMI, IPI, IBMI may also be attributed to the similar effects. The N-coordination in the parent complexes ML₂ (M = Cu, Pd; L = LANI, IAPI) may be the consequence of the strong electron donor property of the substituents X (X = NHC₆H₅, NHC₆H₄CH₃). Similarly the electronic effect could be used to explain N-coordination in the parent complexes PdL₂, where L = IMI, IPI, IBMI. It should be noted, however, that the electronic effects in modifying the bonding mode of the isonitroso group are significant where the steric effects are absent. Thus, the formation of Pd(R-IAI)(IAI') (R = an α-branched alkyl group etc.) may be accounted both by the electronic and the steric effects.

Solvent and temperature: The linkage isomerism of the isonitroso group may be perturbed by the nature of the solvent and the temperature. Only very few complexes are reported which illustrate this fact. Pd(IAI)(IAI') as a solid has asymmetric structure, while in chloroform at refluxing temperature it isomerises to symmetric structure with Pd-N₄ local symmetry¹⁷. This kind of chelate linkage isomerization has been observed only in chloroform. Similarly each of the linkage isomer of XXX and XXXI (M = Ni, R₁ = H, CH₃ and X = CH₃, C₆H₅) isomerizes in chloroform (25-40°C) to give an equilibrium mixture of two linkage isomers¹⁹. Further, the isomerization reactions are irreversible. Solubility difficulties have precluded further studies in different solvents. It is not clear, however, why the corresponding

copper(II) and palladium(II) complexes do not isomerize. High activation energies of the latter complexes appears to be responsible for their failure to isomerize.

The brominated complexes also show tendency to isomerize in chloroform. Thus, the isonitroso N-bonded complex of XXXVI when $R_1 = H$ gives O-bonded isomer in chloroform at room temperature, while the O-bonded isomer with $R_1 = CH_3$ isomerizes to N-bonded isomer. It is rather difficult to explain why such a difference in coordination mode of the isonitroso group arises just on replacement of proton by methyl group.

Although an attempt has been made in the foregoing discussion to explain the factors influencing the ambidentate coordination of the isonitroso group, it has not been possible to explain satisfactorily all the experimental observations. Therefore, it is not clear whether any overall explanation can, or should, be offered. Indeed, the choice of coordination site of the isonitroso group depends on the particular ligand. Thus, the isonitroso group of isonitroso- β -diketones shows normal coordination bonding through nitrogen⁶, the same in the isonitroso- β -ketoimines shows linkage isomerism, depending on several factors as discussed before.

H. Reactions of the Coordinated Isonitroso- β -ketoimines

1. Halogenation

Only one reaction of this type has been reported⁴³. The linkage isomeric mono-nitrosated nickel(II) complexes XXX and XXXI ($R_1 = H, CH_3$ and $X = CH_3$) react with N-bromosuccinimide (NBS) or bromine to give corresponding γ -bromo substituted complexes XXXVII.

The bracket for NO in this structure indicates either N- or O-coordination of the isonitroso group. Interestingly, the N-bonded isomer of XXXVII with $R_1 = H$ transforms into O-bonded isomer in chloroform at room temperature and the O-bonded isomer with $R_1 = CH_3$ isomerizes to N-bonded isomer. These isomerization reactions occur at room temperature.

2. Amine-exchange reactions

Coordinated imine groups are often activated to new Schiff base complex formation on reaction with

primary amines. Such reactions (transamination) can be represented as

The reaction is of interest because of its preparative significance and also in the understanding of biological processes of transamination and deamination^{44,45}. The first amine-exchange reaction was reported for bis(salicylaldimino) copper(II) compounds⁴⁶⁻⁴⁸. The chelates of β -ketoimines, the Schiff bases of β -diketones, are also believed to undergo similar reactions⁴⁴. Recently, metal chelates of isonitroso- β -ketoimines have also been shown to undergo amine-exchange with a variety of primary amines. A summary of the amine-exchange reactions involving isonitroso- β -ketoimines is presented in Table 12.

Some remarks pertaining to the amine-exchange reactions of isonitroso- β -ketoimine complexes can be made here. In contrast to the general behaviour of the β -ketoimine chelates, isonitroso- β -ketoimine complexes undergo facile amine-exchange reactions. Generally, a large excess of amine is required for the reaction. The reaction rate appears to depend on the nature of the amine and the solvent. Qualitatively, the reaction rates are in the decreasing order of $\text{Cu}^{2+} > \text{Pd}^{2+} > \text{Ni}^{2+}$ complexes.

i. *Amine-exchange reactions of nickel(II) complexes*: It can be seen from Table 12 that all the bis(isonitroso- β -ketoimino) nickel(II) complexes react with primary amines yielding mono-alkyl complexes of the general formula $\text{Ni}(\text{R-L})(\text{L}')$ without structural modi-

fication as given by eqn.6. Only the N-H proton

of the five membered ring L of the complexes is substituted, while that of six membered ring L' remains inert under all the amine exchange conditions. The failure of L' to undergo amine-exchange has been ascribed to steric effects^{11,18}. Further, the involvement of N-H in hydrogen bonding with oxygen of the projecting NO in cis position may also be responsible to prevent its reaction.

TABLE 12—AMINE-EXCHANGE REACTIONS INVOLVING BIS(ISONITROSO-β-KETOIMINO) M (II)* COMPLEXES WITH ALKYL OR 1,2-DIAMINES, R-NH₂.

Complex type	M	L = L'	R	Products	Refs.
MLL'	Ni(II)	IAI, IEAI, IMAI, IBI, IANI	alkyl or aryl	Ni(R-L)(L')	11,13
	Pd(II)	IAI	non-bulky alkyl	Pd(R-L) ₂	11,19
ML ₂	Cu(II)	IAI	CH ₃	Cu(Me-IAI) ₂	16
	Cu(II)	IANI, IAPI	alkyl	Cu(R-L) ₂	19
	Pd(II)	IANI, IAPI	alkyl	Pd(R-L) ₂	19
M(R-L)(L')	Ni(II)	IAI, IEAI, IMAI, IBI	H	NiLL'	11,49
MLL'	Ni(II)	IAI, IEAI, IMAI, IBI	NH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂ NH ₂ CH ₂ CH(CH ₃)	Ni(L-E/P-L')	10,13,30
M(R-L)(L')	Cu(II)	IAI	-do-	Cu(IAI-E/P-IAI)	30
	Pd(II)	IAI	-do-	n.r.	30
M(R-L ₁)(L')	Ni(II)	IAL, IEAI, IMAI, IBI	-do-	Ni(L-E/P-L')	10,11,30
M(R-L ₁)(L')	Ni(II)	L' = IAI L ₁ = IEAI, IBI	-do-	Ni(L ₁ -E/P-L')	11

*All the palladium(II) complexes of isonitroso-imine ligands undergo amine-exchange with *N*-alkyl amine yielding corresponding dialkyl complexes¹⁹. n.r. = no reaction.

The reaction (eqn. 3) is reversible and the back reaction can be called reverse amine exchange where ammonia is a reactant. Generally, the rate of forward reaction is faster than the reverse reaction. The reaction of Ni(R-IAI) (IAI') with ammonia has been investigated in detail by Bose⁴⁹. The time required for the backward reaction decreases considerably as the hydrocarbon chain length and bulkiness of R of the reacting amine increases.

Reaction of NiLL' and Ni(R-L) (L') with en/pn yields corresponding tetradentate isonitroso-β-ketoimines, having the ligational environment NiN₃O. The reaction can be represented as

The mixed ligand complexes of the type Ni(R-L₁)(L') also show the same behaviour towards en/pn^{10,11}. Unlike the reaction of NiLL' with primary alkylamines, the tendency of both the imino groups to undergo amine-exchange with diamines may be attributed to the enhanced chelate effect arising from the quadridentate nature of the ligand produced.

ii. *Amine-exchange reactions of copper(II) and palladium(II) complexes.* If the steric factor is solely responsible for the nonformation of Ni(R-L)₂ type complexes, then copper(II) and palladium(II) are expected to form dialkyl complexes as the ionic size of the latter metal ion (0.72 Å for Cu²⁺ and 1.24 Å for Pd²⁺) is less than that of nickel(II) (0.68 Å). The larger ionic size of copper(II) and palladium(II) can reduce the steric hindrance between the projecting >N-O and >N-R groups in cis positions. In fact M(IAI) (IAI') (M=Cu, Pd) gives corresponding dialkyl complexes on reaction with a straight chain alkylamine

as represented below

This reaction, further, involves the rearrangement in coordination of IAI' from isonitroso-oxygen to -nitrogen. The symmetric parent complexes ML₂ (M=Cu, Pd; L = IANI, IAPI) also produce dialkyl complexes¹⁹. Reversible reactions¹⁹ have been observed for Pd(R-L)₂, R=alkyl group and L=IANI, IAPI. Unlike palladium(II) which forms dialkyl complexes with α-branched alkyl amines, the corresponding copper(II) complexes have not been obtained. The failure to prepare di-alkyl copper(II) complexes with α-branched amines has been attributed to the steric effect¹⁹.

The reaction of Cu(IAI)(IAI') with en/pn forming tetradentate ethylene/propylene bridged complexes is accompanied by structural rearrangement from Cu-N₃O to Cu-N₂O₂⁸⁷. Surprisingly, the reaction of Pd (IAI) (IAI') with en/pn has not been observed¹⁸. Steric barrier seems to be the probable cause for the lack of this reaction. However, these complexes have been prepared by different synthetic methods⁸⁷.

From these studies, it has been concluded that the amine-exchange reactions of isonitroso-β-ketoimino-complexes with mono- and di amines are dependent on factors like the size of the metal ion, relative basicities and concentration of the attacking amine, the basicity of the amine(s) liberated during the reaction and steric and chelate effects.

I. Mechanism of the Amine-exchange Reactions

Two different mechanisms have been proposed for the amine-exchange reactions, but both involve the coordinated metal ion whose presence is essential for the rapid reaction. The first mechanism is due to Verter and Frost⁴⁸, which postulates that coordination of the azomethine nitrogen to a metal ion makes the azomethine carbon an electron deficient centre. This facilitates the nucleophilic attack by the exchanging amine. The stepwise mechanism of the amine exchange

reaction can be represented as

FIG 7

This mechanism, as it stands, explains very well the reaction of bis (salicylaldehyde) copper(II) chelates with butylamine but does not explain the failure of amine-exchange reactions of monovalent β -ketoimine chelates, although both the systems have common six membered conjugated rings. Martin⁴⁴ has accounted for this observation by modifying the Verter-Frost mechanism. According to him, the reaction involves the preliminary formation of the monochelated species XXXVIII, as a result of either dissociation or direct formation as shown in Fig. 8.

FIG 8

Subsequently an amine, $R-NH_2$, would react with the monochelated species XXXVIII in the manner suggested by Verter and Frost. A similar dissociative mechanism involving the formation of a monochelated species was suggested by Houghton and Pointer⁵⁰, for the trans-esterification reaction of N -substituted salicylaldehyde metal complexes. The prime factor in the Martin's mechanism, is therefore, the strength of the metal-nitrogen bond. If the bond is strong, the elimination of an amine is less likely. On the other hand, if the bond is comparatively weak, the elimination of an $R'-N$ moiety becomes more likely. Thus, the amine-exchange reaction of the nickel(II) complexes is expected to be faster than that of the copper(II) complexes. However, the reaction of isonitroso β -ketoimine-copper(II) complexes has been found to be faster than the corresponding nickel(II) complexes.

The plausibility of a dissociative mechanism is supported by the observation that the rate of exchange of copper(II) ion with bis (salicylanil) copper(II) is very great⁵¹ and probably involves a dissociative mechanism. According to Martin the resistance of β -ketoimine complexes towards amine-exchange is due to their non-dissociative nature in solution. It has been found that the solution stabilities of these compounds are high⁵².

It is evident from the foregoing discussion that both the Verter-Frost and Martin mechanisms have in common the activation of the azomethine carbon with respect to the nucleophilic attack by an indirect interaction with the metal, which would presumably enhance the positive charge on this atom. The difference between the two mechanisms, however, depends on whether such an activation is achieved by dissociation of the complex or without it. However, it may not be necessary to postulate dissociative type mechanism just to explain the failure of amine-exchange reactions of the β -ketoimine complexes. All the experimental observations can be explained by the Verter-Frost mechanism alone. The non-reactivity of β -ketoimine chelates with primary amines can be attributed to the lack of electrophilicity of the azomethine carbon even after coordination with the metal ion. The mechanism also explains the difference in the reactivity of the free salicylaldehyde and β -ketoimine ligands. Salicylanil XXXIX undergoes amine-exchange, while 4-phenyliminopentane-2-one XL does not. This may be due to the lack of cross resonance in XXXIX as compared to

XL. Moreover, the presence of electron-withdrawing salicyl moiety as well as the hydrogen bonding between the phenolic proton and the nitrogen enhance the positive charge on the azomethine carbon. This facilitates the nucleophilic attack.

The amine-exchange reactions of the bidentate isonitroso- β -ketoimine complexes with primary amines have been explained adequately in the light of Verter-Frost mechanism^{10,11}. A slightly modified mechanism has been proposed for the formation of tetradentate isonitroso- β -ketoimine complexes. The modified mechanistic path is shown in Fig. 9. One of the amino groups of the en/pn attack an azomethine carbon forming mono-iminated chelate XLI. The free amino group of the species XLI can then attack the azomethine carbon of the adjoining chelate ring, producing 1, 2-diamine bridged complex. The formation of such a compound can be explained provided both the imino

Fig. 9

groups are *cis* to each other due to steric reasons. It is, therefore, suggested that the species XLII is produced through 'bond-breaking followed by rotation and bond-making mechanism'. The six membered chelate ring will then undergo amine-exchange in the manner suggested by Verter and Frost yielding XLIII. Recent work of Funke and Melson^{8,9} also supports this kind of mechanism.

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